

CULTURAL GAME JAM KIT

FACILITATOR'S HANDBOOK

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EPIC-WE

Colophon

Deliverable Title: D5.1: EPIC-WE ecosystems, design kits

Document Type: DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

Dissemination Level: PU — Public

Work Package: WP5

Task: T5.1

Lead Beneficiary: NISV

Contributing beneficiary(ies): AU

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Due date of deliverable: 31.01.2025

Actual submission: 23.03.2026

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PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document History:

Version	Date	Status
V1, Internal Draft	22.02.2026	First Draft
V2, Submitted for Review	11.03.2026	Second Draft
V3, Final version after EB and COO Revisions	20.3.2026	Final Draft
V4, Final Version	23.3.2026	Submitted Final Version

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1. Introduction

This *Cultural Game Jam Kit: Facilitators Guide* is a practical tool for partners in the cultural and creative sectors who wish to plan and deliver a Cultural Game Jam (CGJ).

It is inspired by and builds upon the comprehensive EPIC-WE deliverable D3.2 - Protocol 4 titled “EPIC-WE Practical Protocol for Cultural Game Jams in Global Sites (Final protocol)”.

This guide is designed as a *working manual* – a practical companion for facilitators, educators, creative professionals, and cultural organisations. Whether you are from a museum, archive, creative studio, or cultural hub, this guide aims to help you plan, deliver, and evaluate a game jam that integrates cultural heritage, youth empowerment, and creative innovation.

Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) bring together youth citizens (YCs), creative industries (CIs), cultural heritage institutions (CHIs), and (higher) education partners (HEIs) to co-create games inspired by cultural themes and materials.

CGJs are dynamic, inclusive events that harness collective creativity, tackle current social and political issues, examine and interpret European values, and explore new ways of engaging with heritage all with aim of empowering youth voices.

See [Appendix 1](#) for a Master Checklist, helping you organise your own CGJ.

This guide provides a step-by-step structure for facilitators, including:

- ◆ Conceptual foundations and frameworks;
- ◆ Practical planning and execution guidance;
- ◆ Inclusive and empowering facilitation practices;
- ◆ Partner-specific considerations for CHIs and CIs;
- ◆ Templates and checklists for every stage of delivery.

Why Run a 2. Cultural Game Jam?

CGJs fuse the worlds of cultural heritage and youth creativity. They are not just game-making events; they are participatory spaces where cultural identity, imagination, and collaboration converge, cultivating space for youth future-thinking and future-building.

Reasons to Run a Cultural Game Jam:

1 Empowering Youth Participation

- Young people (16–25) become makers of culture, not just consumers.
- Young people develop creative confidence, teamwork, and (digital) storytelling skills.

2 Reimagining Cultural Heritage

- Museums, archives, and heritage institutions can open their collections to new interpretations.
- Games become a medium for exploring values, histories, and identities in innovative ways offering new avenues of storytelling within collections, and as such new potential audiences.

3 Cross-Sector Collaboration

- Cultural and creative industries collaborate with youth, educators, and heritage organisations.

4 Creative Experimentation and Learning

- CGJs promote rapid prototyping, teamwork, and creative problem-solving.
- CGJs are ideal “living lab” environments where experimentation and iteration are encouraged.

5 Building Cultural Futures

- CGJs support the UN Sustainable Development Goals (particularly SDG 4 Quality Education, 5 Gender Equality, 8 Decent Work & Economic Growth, and 11 Sustainable Cities).
- By empowering youth and fostering creative collaboration, CGJs help build more equitable and culturally rich societies, strengthen community connections and contribute to cultural sustainability.

KEY REMINDER:

Cultural Game Jams are not only about producing games – they are about producing meaningful cultural experiences through collaboration.

3. Core Principles and Frameworks

3.1 Quadruple Helix Innovation

At the heart of EPIC-WE's approach is the **Quadruple Helix Cultural Innovation Ecosystem**, which brings together four helix partners:

- Government and policy-makers
- Industry (Creative and Cultural Sectors)
- Academia (Higher Education Institutions)
- Citizens (particularly youth)

Each "helix" contributes unique expertise.

In the context of a CGJ:

- CHIs bring cultural resources and heritage expertise.
- CIs contribute design and technological skills.
- HEIs provide structure, reflection, and educational value.
- Youth citizens offer creativity, lived experience, and new perspectives.

3.2 Cultural Game Jams: Games as, for, and through Culture

Cultural Game Jams explore culture in three ways:

- 1 **Games as culture** – games as creative cultural expressions.
- 2 **Games for culture** – games made to foster understanding or dialogue about cultural values.
- 3 **Games through culture** – games created using heritage collections or cultural materials.

This triadic approach ensures that each CGJ links directly to cultural narratives while enabling diverse creative interpretations.

3.3 Inclusive and Transversal Design

Inclusivity is not a checklist but an ethos. Facilitators should ensure that every participant, regardless of background, identity, or ability, can fully engage. This involves:

- Using inclusive language and practices;
- Providing accessible spaces and materials;
- Recognising and responding to diverse neurotypes and physical abilities;
- Actively including underrepresented voices.

Transversal design promotes creative collaboration across differences, thus enabling a "we" of collective creativity to emerge. For more on inclusive design in Cultural Game Jams please read the article '*DESIGNING WITH AMBIGUITY: Iterating Equity in Game Jam Design*'.

[Read the article](#)

Designing and Executing a 4. Cultural Game Jam

4.1 Planning Timeline

The planning of a CGJ can be easily divided into 3 phases: *Before*, *During* and *After* the game jam.

	Focus	Key Actions
Before	Define purpose, recruit, plan logistics	Identify partners, select theme, recruit youth, plan inclusion measures
During	Facilitate collaboration and creation	Support teams, manage logistics, foster inclusivity and creativity
After	Evaluate and extend impact	Debrief, document outcomes, plan dissemination and follow-on projects

Checklist Pre-Jam:

- Define theme and objectives.
- Confirm roles and responsibilities across partners and teams.
- Recruit youth participants and mentors.
- Prepare spaces, materials, and accessibility arrangements.
- Develop communication channels for participants (e.g., Discord).
- Schedule all sessions and prepare facilitation kits.

4.2 Defining the Problem Space and Theme

The “Problem Space” defines the scope of your game jam – what cultural question or challenge it addresses. Themes, for example, may focus on:

- Cultural identity and belonging
- Social inclusion and European values
- Environmental heritage and sustainability
- Artistic reinterpretation of heritage collections

Tips!

- Keep the theme simple and meaningful.
- Avoid overloading participants with both too many constraints & too many options. Find the sweet spot between the two.
- Provide clear examples of how heritage materials can be used.

4.3 Roles and Responsibilities

Each partner contributes to the jam ecosystem in different ways based on their expertise. Below is a general overview of how this division of labour could look, bearing in mind that different partners (specifically the CHI, CI and HEI listed below) often share competencies and expertise, or might operate differently than the example listed below:

	Role	Examples of Responsibilities
CHI	Facilitator of cultural heritage materials	Provide access to collections, contextual expertise, and space for the CGJ
CI	Creative design and production	Facilitate creative tools, mentorship, and game-making expertise
HEI	Educational scaffolding and research	Support reflection, documentation, and evaluation
Youth Citizens (YCs)	Co-creators	Design, ideate, and produce game prototypes

4.4 Designing for Inclusion and Accessibility

Inclusion should be considered and visible in every aspect – recruitment, space design, communication, and facilitation.

Inclusion Principles:

- Ask participants in advance about accessibility needs.
- Ensure physical, sensory, and cognitive accessibility.
- Provide quiet spaces, pronoun options, and inclusive language.
- Offer financial or travel support if possible to enable participation in the event.
- Debrief inclusion successes and missteps, and document lessons learned on inclusion for future jams.

4.5 Recruitment and Participant Engagement

Recruitment should reflect the diversity of your community. Combine open calls with targeted outreach through schools, youth networks, and creative communities.

Recruitment Checklist:

- Define the age range and participant criteria.
- Use youth-friendly communication (Instagram, TikTok, Discord).
- Connect directly with students already in partner networks (e.g. school classes, etc)
- Involve Youth Advisory Board members as ambassadors.
- Clearly explain the value of participation (“What’s in it for me?”).
- Confirm participants’ needs, permissions, and availability early.

4.6 Jam Format and Structure

Cultural Game Jams can be organised in different time formats. What organisers choose often relates to what they can accommodate in their facilities in combination with the availability of the particular participant group they are targeting. For example, if you are doing an open call for students, it is usually not ideal to run a week-long jam during the school year as this will decrease student availability.

However, if you are collaborating with a particular class of students that already exists at a school, it could be possible to connect the class to the CGJ, having students receive credit for it, and run it during class time.

It is important to understand the rough availability of your intended recruits as you devise the format.

Common formats for CGJs include:

- **48-hour jam:** Intense, collaborative sprint (great for open calls).
- **Week-long jam:** Easiest if integrated with education programmes, or run as a winter or summer school during the holidays (however recruit holiday plans or job schedules might impede their participation).
- **Extended Jam:** Hybrid online/offline over multiple weeks.

See [Appendix 2](#) for an example of a **CGJ Schedule (48-hour sprint)**.

Image: Cultural Game Jam at Sound & Vision, 2025

4.7 Jam Structure, CGJ Toolkit & Facilitation Materials

The CGJ Kits offers in-depth understanding of the CGJ phases and the different methods and tools that could be employed. Familiarise yourself with the different options for devising the structure of the content of your Cultural Game Jam. Download the full playbook below.

[Download CGJ Kits](#)

As a CGJ organiser, provide a **Jam Brief** upfront to participants, outlining the scope, theme, expectations, deliverables such as a prototype and pitch, timeline of the CGJ, as well as jury judging criteria.

See [Appendix 3](#) for an example of a **Game Jam Brief**, [Appendix 4](#) for an example of **Pitch Prep Instructions**, and [Appendix 5](#) for an example of **Jury Evaluation Criteria**.

Each jam should include the following topics regardless of the format:

- Kick-off and introductions:** Welcome participants, introduce partners, and outline the theme, goals, and schedule. Set expectations, establish a safe and inclusive environment, and provide an overview of cultural materials and available support.
- Team formation:** Facilitate the creation of diverse teams based on interests and skills. Encourage balanced collaboration across disciplines and ensure all participants feel comfortable, included, and able to contribute.
- Idea development:** Support teams in exploring the theme and generating concepts. Encourage experimentation, connection to cultural materials, and clear articulation of ideas through discussion, sketching, or simple concept pitches.
- Game design and prototyping:** Guide teams in developing their ideas into playable prototypes. Encourage iterative design, use of accessible tools, and collaboration between creative, technical, and storytelling roles.
- Playtesting and feedback:** Create opportunities for teams to test each other's games and gather feedback. Encourage constructive critique, reflection, and iteration to improve gameplay, clarity, and cultural relevance.
- Final presentations:** Teams present their games through short pitches and demonstrations. Highlight key ideas, design choices, and connections to the theme, while celebrating creativity and diverse approaches.
- Reflection and celebration:** Facilitate a closing session to reflect on experiences, learning outcomes, and collaboration. Celebrate all contributions, acknowledge achievements, and encourage continued engagement beyond the jam.

4.8 Space, Logistics and Production Materials

Some general practical needs for CGJs include:

- **Accessible venue with flexible workspace:** Ensure the venue is accessible and adaptable. Provide spaces for group work and quieter breakout areas to support different needs and working styles.
- **Power, Wi-Fi, and digital equipment:** Provide stable internet, sufficient power outlets, and key equipment such as laptops, projectors, and audio tools for development and communication.
- **Whiteboards, post-its, art supplies for prototyping:** Offer simple materials for brainstorming and prototyping. These support quick idea development, visual thinking, and collaboration across skill levels.
- **Food and refreshments:** Provide meals, snacks, and drinks throughout the jam. Consider dietary needs and create moments for participants to connect and recharge.
- **Quiet and rest areas:** Provide calm spaces for breaks or focused work. These support wellbeing, reduce overstimulation, and help participants stay engaged.

Tip!

Plan the physical layout to encourage collaboration while respecting individual needs.

4.9 Facilitation and Communication

Facilitators are the glue of the jam. Their role is to enable, not direct, creating space for participants to collaborate and explore freely. Facilitator Reminders:

- Foster a welcoming, inclusive atmosphere.
- Support teams equally and encourage idea diversity.
- Manage time but allow flexibility.
- Use tools like Discord or Miro for coordination.
- Celebrate every contribution.

4.10 Evaluation and Follow-up

Evaluation ensures that learning and impact are captured and support further iterations of your CGJs.

What to Evaluate:

- Participant experience and empowerment.
- Quality and cultural depth of games produced.
- Collaboration and inclusion effectiveness.
- Youth learning outcomes and skills gained.

Follow-up Actions:

- Share outcomes with participants and partners.
- Consider further development of promising prototypes.
- Invite participants to join Youth Assemblies or creative networks for further collaboration.

Designing and Running a 5. Youth Advisory Board

5.1 Conceptual Foundations

Youth Advisory Board (YABs), as developed in EPIC-WE, provide structures for empowered participation. They recognise youth not as end-users but as equal partners in cultural innovation.

5.2 Practical Implementation Step-by-Step:

- 1 Define Purpose:** Clarify how the YA will support the jam (e.g., advising on themes, testing inclusivity, time expectations).
- 2 Recruit Diverse Members:** Include youth (16–25) with varied cultural, gender, and educational backgrounds.
- 3 Facilitate Regular Meetings:** Combine online discussions with in-person workshops, accommodating YA member schedules.
- 4 Give Real Influence:** Involve YAs in real decision-making (themes, formats, evaluation).
- 5 Ensure Continuity:** Keep YAs active between jams to sustain engagement.

5.3 YC Integration into the Game Jam Cycle

YCs should be given the opportunity to be active in the full cycle of the CGJ. Below provides some ideas to support the inclusion of YCs and/or YAB in different phases of planning and execution.

- **Before the Jam:** Co-design themes, recruitment strategies, and inclusion measures.
- **During:** Serve as peer mentors or observers.
- **After:** Evaluate experiences, advise on improvements, and act as ambassadors.

Checklist: Youth Advisory Board Setup

- 8–12 members, 50/50 gender balance minimum.
- Clear role descriptions.
- Facilitation by youth liaison (from CHI or CI partner).
- Feedback loop to jam organisers.
- Opportunities for leadership and public representation.

6. Empowering Youth Participants

Beyond End-Users

Empowerment means shifting from participation *in* culture to participation *as* culture-makers.

Key Strategies:

- 1 Involve youth in decision-making and design.
- 2 Provide mentorship opportunities.
- 3 Offer creative ownership and visibility.
- 4 Encourage reflection and storytelling about their process.

REMINDER for Facilitators:

- Ask, don't tell: Youth-led exploration builds ownership.
- Highlight that every contribution matters.
- Work to build safer and braver spaces for participants to experiment within.
- Frame failures as an integral part of the experimentation and innovation process.

Image: Cultural Game Jam at Sound & Vision, 2024

7. Partner Roles and Priorities

7.1 Creative Industries

The role of the Creative Industry (CI) partner can vary, however, there are generally some key areas of support that they provide, such as:

- Bring technical expertise in design, coding, and prototyping.
- Support creative ideation and innovation processes.
- Offer mentorship and exposure to industry standards.
- Help translate cultural ideas into engaging interactive experiences.

The below table provides a suggested overview of the different tasks the partners could be involved in during.

7.2 Cultural Heritage Institution

The role of the Cultural Heritage Institute (CHI) partner can vary as well, however, there are generally some key areas of support that they provide, such as:

- Provide cultural collections, historical context, and thematic grounding.
- Host the event or contribute venue space.
- Ensure that heritage materials are used ethically and creatively.
- Foster cultural reflection through workshops or exhibitions.

See [Appendix 6](#) for a more elaborate table with **Roles and Priorities**.

	CI Partner Tasks	CHI Partner Tasks
Before	Co-design jam format, mentor recruitment, participant recruitment, tech setup	Select and prepare cultural materials; brief facilitators
During	Facilitate design sprints, mentor CGJ teams, troubleshoot	Guide participants in interpreting collections
After	Support evaluation, documentation, and prototype development	Archive outputs; explore exhibition or dissemination opportunities

8. Evaluation and Sustainability

The evaluation of a CGJ should measure both the process and impact. Potential indicators of success to measure could include:

- Level and quality of Youth empowerment and agency
- Quality of collaboration amongst organisers and/or youth teams
- Cultural and creative outcomes of the CGJ (e.g. levels of integration of cultural materials, social/cultural issues, etc)
- Inclusivity and accessibility
- Long-term relationships between partners

The impact of a CGJ can also be explored through the lens of sustainability—the extent to which the presence and impact of a CGJ extend beyond its actual execution. Some actions to take towards sustainability could include:

- Build ongoing partnerships between CHI, CI, and HEI sectors.
- Document and share best practices.
- Integrate CGJs into local and national cultural calendars.
- Maintain alumni and youth ambassador networks.

See [Appendix 7](#) for the complete **Evaluation Checklist**.

9. Conclusion

and Continuing Practices

Cultural Game Jams are more than events – they are evolving laboratories for cultural co-creation. They bring together sectors, generations, and disciplines to experiment with how culture can be played, made, and imagined anew, and how the creation and playing of games can and should be taken seriously as a means through which to empower youth to think through and imagine their present and future.

As a facilitator, you play a vital role: you hold the space, enable creativity, and translate frameworks into action. By following the principles outlined here—you can create Cultural Game Jams that are inclusive, inspiring, meaningful and transformative.

Final Reminder:

Keep adapting! Each jam is a living experiment—reflect, learn, and evolve your practice.

Curious to read more on EPIC-WE? Take a look at the complete repository on our project website.

[Repository](#)

Image: Cultural Game Jam at Sound & Vision, 2025

APPENDIX

FACILITATOR QUICK- REFERENCE GUIDES

MASTER CHECKLIST

CGJ Planning, Execution & Evaluation

Below provides a practical overview of key actions and responsibilities across all stages of the Cultural Game Jam.

BEFORE THE JAM

- Define the Foundations:** identify purpose, theme, partners and their roles, budget, dates, and venue.
- Design for Inclusion:** accessibility planning, inclusive materials, pronoun options, quiet zones.
- Recruit and Engage:** youth-friendly and pointed outreach, Youth Advisory Board engagement, consent forms.
- Develop Jam Design and Materials:** prepare Jam Brief, event and facilitator schedule, facilitator toolkits and facilitation materials, evaluation rubrics
- Execute Pre-production Actions:** secure venue and rooms, prepare technological requirements, procure prototyping materials, book food and drinks.
- Prepare the Evaluation Process:** define criteria, pre/post surveys, assign evaluation roles.

DURING THE JAM

- Opening & Orientation:** introductions, inclusivity overview, present Jam Brief.
- Team Formation and Ideation:** balanced team creation, youth leadership, mentorship.
- Development and Prototyping:** monitor progress, support inclusion, provide technical help.
- Testing and Refinement:** playtesting, feedback rounds, documentation.
- Final Presentations:** pitches, evaluations, celebration of achievements.

AFTER THE JAM

- Debrief and Reflect:** facilitator meeting, participant feedback, inclusion reflection.
- Evaluate Outcomes:** assess cultural and creative outputs, youth empowerment, diversity.
- Disseminate and Continue Engagement:** share outcomes, sustain Youth Advisory Board, archive outputs.

Sample CGJ Schedule

TEMPLATE: 48-hour sprint

The below provides an example of a CGJ schedule for a 48-hour sprint.

	Activity	Focus
Day 1 - Morning	Welcome & Orientation	Introductions, theme, materials
Day 1 - Afternoon	EXPERIENCE PHASE Team Formation & Start Developing Game Ideas	Team setup and brainstorming
Day 1 - Evening	PLAY PHASE Initial Prototyping of Concepts & Expert Council	Sketching and pitching game idea to a panel of experts
Day 2 - Morning	IMAGINE PHASE Development Sprint	Building (paper) prototypes, mentorship by professionals
Day 2 - Afternoon	IMAGINE PHASE - Continued Playtesting & Iteration	Peer feedback and iteration
Day 3 - Morning	CREATE PHASE itch.io Submissions & Final Presentations	Finalizing game for submission, pitch prep, and Jury showcase
Day 3 - Afternoon	Reflection & Closing	Evaluation, celebration

Game Jam Brief

Example

Below offers an example of a CGJ Brief. This document is developed to ensure that participants have an overarching understanding of the event and their participation, and what is expected of them as participants.

Game Jam Brief

In this cultural game jam, you will go through four phases and combine four elements: art and culture, European values, game design, and citizenship. You will design a value-based cultural game prototype and/or concept based on at least one European value, a cultural heritage material, and relate it to a societal challenge. During the jam, you will move through four different ideation and development phases: experience, play, imagine, and create, with a transition tool aiding the move from one phase to another.

The overarching theme of this cultural game jam is **“That’s Not Fair”**, which emphasises that inequality is not merely an obstacle – it is the very foundation of numerous systems that shape our lives. These imbalances affect how we access resources, interact with others, and envisage our future.

As the European Union grapples with increasing polarisation and crises related to climate, housing, and the cost of living, understanding fairness is now more crucial than ever. By exploring themes such as the wealth gap, social inclusion, and climate justice through games and culture, we encourage young game-makers to ignite more profound, playful, and empathetic conversations about what equality truly means to youth today.

This means that your team will design and deliver a value-based and cultural game:

- As a **game concept and/or prototype**;
- That integrates at least one of the **European values**;
- And is inspired by at least one piece of **cultural heritage material**;
- Which connects to **youth citizenship**, highlighting your voices and broader perspectives on culture and society;
- Connects to the jam theme: **“That’s Not Fair”**;
- That is uploaded to the platform **itch.io**;
- With **game logs** from each of the four phases showing your process and reflections.

You will also:

- Prepare a **5-minute pitch** about your game following the pitch guidelines & evaluation criteria shared.

Pitch Prep Instructions

Example

The following offers text that could be used in Pitch Prep Instructions. The purpose of these instructions is to support participants in preparing for their pitch. The instructions are also useful as they outline for participants what is expected of them regarding the things they should have considered in their game prototype.

Pitch

A pitch is a short and engaging presentation that clearly explains why your concept is unique. The pitch should excite the audience about the game and its possibilities. Use the following steps to prepare an engaging pitch of about 5 minutes. The following topics should be covered:

- 1 **Theme & Values: How does your game align with the theme of the game jam?**
Explain how the theme [THEME] is reflected in the game through the storyline, challenges, and interactions. Show how the theme is integrated into the game mechanics and objectives.
- 2 **Concept: Story, goal, and characters**
Create a compelling story for your game. Introduce the main characters

and their motivations in relation to the theme of the cultural game jam. Describe the setting and key plot points. Explain what the characters are trying to achieve and what obstacles they face.

- 3 **Design: Look & feel, game mechanics, and playability**
Describe the game mechanics and design elements. Explain how players interact with the game, the rules, and the objectives. Highlight any unique features or innovations in the game. Clarify whether the game has a clear ending or an open-ended structure. Discuss how players can win or achieve goals in the game.
- 4 **Cultural Material: Integrating cultural material into your game**
Explain how the [CULTURAL MATERIAL] has inspired the game. Perhaps a [GIVE EXAMPLES OF THE WAY THE CULTURAL MATERIAL COULD HAVE INSPIRED]. Describe how the [CULTURAL MATERIAL] has influenced the concept, setting, mechanics, and visual style of the game.

Final Tips!

- Be concise & impactful
- Use visuals
- Engage your audience
- Practice, practice, practice!

Evaluation Criteria

Example

You will see the following Pitch/Game evaluation criteria, shared with both participants and the jury, clearly outlines how the games are judged. These award criteria build on the expectations as laid out in the Game Jam Brief and the Pitch Prep Instructions as an example of how to offer participants a “through line” in their CGJ participation.

Jury Evaluation Criteria

The jury will evaluate all games during the pitches based on the following criteria. Your game can score a maximum of five stars per category. Who will take home the awards?!

1

Theme & Values

How well does your game align with the game jam theme?

1. No clear link to the theme
2. Weakly linked to the theme
3. Moderately linked to the theme
4. Creatively linked to the theme
5. Extremely creative link to the theme

2

Concept

Are the story and characters well thought out and creative?

1. No clear game concept
2. Weak game concept
3. Decent game concept
4. Creative and clear game concept
5. Extremely creative game concept

3

Design

Does the game look good, is it playable, and do the mechanics work well?

1. Poor design + not playable
2. Weak design + playable
3. Decent design + playable
4. Good design + well playable
5. Excellent design + very well playable

4

Cultural Material

Does the [CULTURAL MATERIAL] play a strong role in the game?

1. Not connected to the collection
2. Weak connection to the collection
3. Decent connection to the collection
4. Strong connection to the collection
5. Excellent connection to the collection

Roles & Responsibilities

TEMPLATE: Roles & Responsibilities Snapshot

Below provides a brief overview of the potential roles and responsibilities required, and taken up by different partner participants.

	Description	Examples of Tasks
Team Leader (CHI or CI partner)	Oversee planning and flow	Master schedule, communicate with CGJ planning & execution team
CHI Partner	Provide heritage context	Select cultural materials, prepare briefs for participants on the materials
CI Partner	Provide creative and technical guidance	Mentorship/facilitation, design tools, prototype further-development
HEI Partner	Supports learning and evaluation	Documentation, reflection
Youth Advisory Board	Advisory and peer engagement	Recruitment input, planning input, peer mentoring
Logistics Coordinator *	Venue, catering, accessibility	Setup, safety, catering
Media/Comms Lead	Communications and documentation	Outreach, event photos
Evaluation Lead	Leads evaluation and reporting	Surveys, debriefs

* usually from the venue organisation, likely CHI

Evaluation Checklist

Participant Experience

- Did participants feel empowered and included?
- Was communication clear and accessible?
- Were youth voices integrated?
- Did participants gain new skills?

Collaboration and Process

- Were all partners active throughout?
- Was collaboration respectful and effective?
- Did facilitation support inclusion?

Game Outputs

- Were games aligned with the theme?
- Did they creatively use cultural materials?

Inclusion and Accessibility

- Were accessibility needs met?
- Was diversity represented?
- Were neurodiverse participants supported?

Legacy and Impact

- Were next steps defined for prototypes?
- Did partnerships continue beyond the jam?

